

Revolutionizing Endodontics: Direct Pulp Capping with TheraCal PT

¹Dr. Radhika Charhate, Post Graduate student at Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur.

²Dr. Vandana Gade, Professor at Conservative Dentistry And Endodontics, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College And Hospital, Nagpur.

Abstract

The case describes the use of TheraCal PT (BISCO) as a direct pulp capping agent for small pulpal exposure during caries excavation in permanent molars. After a clinical examination, pulp sensibility test, and radiographic examinations, the teeth were diagnosed with reversible pulpitis. Caries were removed, and TheraCal PT was placed in the patient's teeth, followed by composite resin restoration. At the one-week follow-up, the patient's spontaneous symptoms had resolved in the case.

INTRODUCTION

The pulp tissue has a natural ability to heal if it is healthy. Even after being exposed to decay, the pulp can heal as long as the inflammation indicates reversible pulpitis.¹

Treatment options for a pulpal exposure in a tooth include direct pulp capping (DPC), pulpotomy, and pulpectomy. According to the American Association of Endodontics (AAE), direct pulp capping (DPC) is the direct application of biocompatible medicaments on an exposed pulp site, particularly in cases of mechanical or traumatic exposure.^{1,2}

The use of hydraulic calcium silicate cement has made vital pulp therapy (VPT) more predictable.

Ca(OH)₂ has long been considered the gold standard, but the invention of Mineral Trioxide Aggregate (MTA) by Torabinejad has led to its wider usage in clinical practice. The favorable properties of silicate-based materials have spurred the development of new material compositions, including resin-modified calcium silicate-based materials.³

Recently, a biocompatible, dual-cure resin-modified calcium silicate-based material called TheraCal PT (Bisco, USA) has been introduced. According to its manufacturer, it is mainly for pulpotomies and can also be used for direct pulp capping.³

TheraCal PT consists of a chemical formulation that includes synthetic Portland cement, calcium silicate particles in a hydrophilic matrix that enables the release of calcium. Its calcium release properties and the ability to create an alkaline pH make it suitable for use in deep cavity preparations.^{4,5,6}

The dual-cure ability allows for immediate placement of the restorative material.

CASE REPORT

- A female patient, aged 23 years, reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with the chief complaint of sensitivity in the lower left back region for the last two weeks. The patient experienced sharp pain on consumption of cold beverages which lasted momentarily and was relieved a few seconds later.

On clinical examination, occlusal caries in relation to tooth number 36 was observed. IOPA revealed radiolucency on the occlusal aspect of 36 involving enamel, dentin and approaching pulp.

- Tooth 36 responded positively to pulp sensitivity test with ethyl chloride spray (Endo frost, Coltene), thus indicating that the tooth was vital. The medical history of the patient was non contributory. 36 was diagnosed with Acute reversible pulpitis.

PRE-OPERATIVE RADIOGRAPH

Selected tooth was administrated with local anaesthesia with (2% lignocaine with 1:80,000 adrenaline). Tooth was isolated with a rubber dam.

Nonselective caries excavation was performed from the periphery towards the center with round bur (BR 31, mani, Japan).

After approximating near the pulp, a sharp spoon excavator (Dentsply b190) was used for the removal of residual caries.

PRE-OPERATIVE PHOTOGRAPH

To control the bleeding, a sterile cotton pellet moistened with 3% sodium hypochlorite (Prime) was placed for 5 minutes. The tooth was then rinsed with saline to remove any excess sodium hypochlorite. Subsequently, a new set of sterile instruments was used to minimize contamination from carious debris to the exposed site and the capping material.

PULPAL EXPOSURE

TheraCal PT (BISCO), 1.5–2 mm thick, was applied to the site of pulpal exposure..

The tooth was successfully restored using composite resin (Prime, restorite nano hybrid) on the same day. The patient was asked to return after 7 days for a follow-up exam, including clinical and radiographic assessments.

During the follow-up appointment, a clinical assessment was performed to check for sensitivity, pain, swelling, mobility, tenderness on percussion, and the presence of a sinus tract. The pulp sensitivity test conducted at this follow-up showed positive results.

And radiographic assessment was done to assess the signs of periapical pathology.

FOLLOWUP RADIOGRAPH AFTER 7 DAYS

DISCUSSION:

The DPC (Direct Pulp Capping) technique is used to cover the exposed pulp area by applying a biocompatible medicament directly over it. This technique helps maintain the health and function of the pulp by inducing the formation of reparative dentin through dentin bridge formation.⁷ The American Association of Endodontists has stated that DPC should only be applied to mechanically or traumatically exposed pulp. However, some reports suggest that there is no difference in DPC outcomes between carious teeth with and without pulp exposure.^{7,8}

A systematic review by Aguilar and Linsuwanont has shown that DPC can successfully treat permanent carious teeth with pulp exposure. Bogen et al. reported an overall pulpal survival rate of 97.96% among 40 patients (49 teeth) who underwent pulp capping treatment with MTA (Mineral Trioxide Aggregate).⁹

The DPC material should stimulate the regeneration of the dentin-pulp complex, induce the differentiation of odontoblast-like cells, and demonstrate biocompatibility, antibacterial, and non-toxic properties. Although calcium hydroxide has been used in the past, MTA was introduced by Torabinejad and Chivian as the first calcium silicate cement in 1990. Both materials are effective for treating carious exposure in permanent teeth. However, MTA is considered more effective due to its biocompatibility, ability to maintain a high pH for a longer duration, induce dentin bridge formation, reduce pulpal inflammatory response, and form an insoluble barrier to prevent microleakage.^{10,11}

CONCLUSION:

Direct pulp capping using MTA, a commonly used material, and the recently introduced TheraCal PT (a dual cure calcium silicate) have shown positive results in a 7-day follow-up. The affected tooth's vitality was preserved, and the patient remained asymptomatic.

REFERENCES:

1. Sameia MM, Darrag AM, Ghoneim WM. Two calcium silicate-based materials used in direct pulp capping (in-vivo study). *Tanta Dental Journal*. 2020;1;17(2):78.
2. Kunert M, Lukomska-Szymanska M. Bio-Inductive Materials in Direct and Indirect Pulp Capping-A Review Article. *Materials (Basel)*. 2020 7;13(5):1204.
3. Bogen G, Kim JS, Bakland LK. Direct pulp capping with mineral trioxide aggregate: an observational study. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2008;139(3):305-15; quiz 305-15.
4. Sanz JL, Soler-Doria A, Lopez-Garcoa S, Garcia-Bernal D, Rodriguez-Lozano FJ, Lozano A, Llena C, Forner L, Guerrero-Girones J, Melo M. Comparative Biological Properties and Mineralization Potential of 3 Endodontic Materials for Vital Pulp Therapy: Theracal PT, Theracal LC, and Biodentine on Human Dental Pulp Stem Cells. *J Endod*. 2021;47(12):1896-1906.
5. Al-Hiyasat AS, Barrieshi-Nusair KM, Al-Omari MA. The radiographic outcomes of direct pulp-capping procedures performed by dental students: a retrospective study. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2006;137(12):1699-705.
6. Horsted P, Sandergaard B, Thylstrup A, El Attar K, Fejerskov O. A retrospective study of direct pulp capping with calcium hydroxide compounds. *Endod Dent Traumatol*. 1985;1(1):29-34
7. Hilton TJ. Keys to clinical success with pulp capping: a review of the literature. *Oper Dent*. 2009;34(5):615-625.
8. Voicu G, Didilescu AC, Stoian AB, Dumitriu C, Greabu M, Andrei M. Mineralogical and

Microstructural Characteristics of Two Dental Pulp Capping Materials. *Materials (Basel)*. 2019;12(11):1772.

9. Torabinejad M, Watson TF, Pitt Ford TR. Sealing ability of a mineral trioxide aggregate when used as a root end filling material. *J Endod*. 1993;19(12):591-5

10. Tuzuner T, Alacam A, Altunbas DA, Gokdogan FG, Gundogdu E. Clinical and radiographic outcomes of direct pulp capping therapy in primary molar teeth following haemostasis with various antiseptics: a randomised controlled trial. *Eur J Paediatr Dent*. 2012;13(4):289-92.

11. Gandolfi MG, Siboni F, Prati C. Chemical–physical properties of TheraCal, a novel light-curable MTA-like material for pulp capping. *Int Endodont J*. 2012;45(6):571–579.

12. Morotomi T, Washio A, Kitamura C. Current and future options for dental pulp therapy. *Jap Dent Sci Rev*. 2019;55(1):5–11.

13. Erfanparast L, Iranparvar P, Vafaei A. Direct pulp capping in primary molars using a resin-modified Portland cement-based material (TheraCal) compared to MTA with 12-month follow-up: a randomised clinical trial. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent*. 2018;19(3):197–203.

14. Asl Aminabadi N, Satrab S, Najafpour E, et al. A randomized trial of direct pulp capping in primary molars using MTA compared to 3Mixtatin: a novel pulp capping biomaterial. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2016;26(4):281–290.

15. Jha S, Goel N, Dash BP, et al. An update on newer pulpotomy agents in primary teeth: a literature review. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci*. 2021;13(Suppl 1):S57–S61.